

MODULAR TEACHING TECHNOLOGY BASED ON SCIENCE-BASED APPROACH TO ACTIVITY

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Annotation: modular teaching dictates the reading of problematic and difficult lectures that provide generalized information on the major issues of science.

Lectures should focus on developing students' creative abilities. The practical and laboratory classes of the module are formed together with the lectures, which supplement the content of the lectures with a new material from which they will be studied. Students will have practical skills.

Base words: science, module, macromodule, consortium, MKM.

Science activity approach module in the Education Science system refers to the application of the methodology. The technology of such modular training in the system of higher education in academic lists and professional colleges, educators and the purpose of application in systems of professional development of engineers and pedagogues it is appropriate.

In modular teaching technology based on the approach of activity in science the module itself embodies the following:

- fundamental concepts of educational science - a certain phenomenon, or law, or section, or a major topic, or a group of interrelated concepts;
- to study one or more fundamental concepts of educational science it is aimed at (mastering).

Usually the module will consist of 3-6 hours of lecture sessions and related practical (workshop), laboratory classes.

Based on a strictly systematic (multifaceted) analysis of the apparatus of explanation of Science, the most an effective module is formed. And this is the separation of the group of fundamental phrases, material provides the ability to group logically and compactly.

Since the module is an independent structural unit, in some cases, it gives individual readers the opportunity to listen to a series of modules, not just to scan the fan. This gives rise to the possibility of optimal planning of individual and independent work of senior students.

In modular teaching, the curriculum is complete, concise and through deepening stratification, there is an opportunity to stratify the teaching there will be, that is, it will be possible to individualize training.

The following objectives are pursued in the transition to modular teaching:

- ensuring continuity of teaching (between subjects and within science);
- individualization of training;
- to create sufficient conditions for the independent mastering of the educational material;
- accelerate training;
- achieve effective mastering of science.

Thus, according to the students ' own abilities in modular teaching full necessary conditions are created for the acquisition of knowledge.

The effectiveness of the transition of training to the modular system, to the following factors will depend:

- the level of material and technical base of the educational institution;
- qualification level of professors and teachers;
- students ' level of preparation;
- evaluation of the results;
- didactic materials development;
- analysis of results and optimization of modules.

In the transition to modular training, it is envisaged to carry out:

-on the basis of an in-depth analysis of the working plan, the interrelated disciplines are determined by a group of closely related subjects, namely the entire working plan is regarded as a separate set of macromodules.

In the vast majority of cases, the following three types of macromodules can be formed:

- a) which includes humanities;
- b) Economic Sciences including;
- C) which includes general education, general technical, General professional and specialty subjects.

In the formation of a specialist of any macromodule, his own goal and the function is. The purpose of studying a specific macromodule, which enters into it it follows from the study objectives of the sciences.

A set of learning objectives of any macromodule, public education reflected in the standards, set up the main purpose of specialist training will. The purpose of any macromodule is clearly structured, the science of the first when it begins to be studied, it must be delivered to the students. Each of the macromodules when the next science begins to be studied, it is the objectives of the study of science that students will be brought to your attention:

-within which macromodule sequences are acceptable, within which the subjects are studied, the duration of each series and their study are established. That is, by ensuring the continuity of teaching, it is necessary to achieve a reduction in the duration of the study of Sciences and thereby the duration of the study of macromodule. Subjects with the size of training hours are not on the floor (1-2 classes per week, in some cases 3-hour audience), are included in the list of block subjects, are desirable, and they can be passed in the first or second half of the training semester.

Based on the calculation of vertical close interdependence of macromodules they are formed, but when setting the periods of their study, horizontal connections between macromodules should be taken into account.

-in order to prevent duplication of the instructional material, interdependence of macromodular disciplines, educational programs will be provided.

Modular training technology based on a systematic activity approach.

Systematic activity approach is the study of the activity of a specialist, the list the educational disciplines in which it is necessary to study to carry out activities, determination of the content of educational materials, the structure of modules and the educational process characterized by Organization.

Systematic business approach to modular technology, first of all professional it is used in education. A vivid example of this is Unesco International modules of labor skills "Modules of labor skills(MCM) is a" constipation".

Counseling, without division into educational disciplines, to holistic teaching it is distinguished by its orientation.

The advantages of the concept are that the design process of the technologies of modules is a clear composition and a complete formation of the form of educational-software documentation in the modular variant.

MCM-modular program of training, analysis of specialist activities, it is formed on the basis of the study of its content and composition, and modular blocks, as well as the tutorial will consist of a collection of modules.

Production activities of a specialist include the fulfillment of a number of production tasks. They, in turn, will consist of production activities (steps of work), which will be performed in the specified sequence. In order to perform the actions that are part of the production task, the worker must have a certain level of theoretical knowledge and practical skills.

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